

What is the resource footprint of a computer science department? Place, people and pedagogy.

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Abstract

Increasingly interconnected Internet and Communication Technology (ICT)/electrical and electronic equipment (EEE)-related products, processes, services and infrastructure are the bedrock of today’s knowledge economy. This ecosystem of machine-to-machine and cyber-physical-system technologies has myriad direct and indirect impacts on the lithosphere, biosphere, atmosphere, and hydrosphere. As key determinants of tomorrow’s digital technologies, academic computer science departments worldwide are critical sites for exploring ways to mitigate and/or eliminate the negative impacts. We report the first case study to address the question “How do we create more resilient and healthier computer science departments: living laboratories for teaching and learning about resource-constrained computing, computation, and communication?” Specifically, we outline a roadmap and propose high-level principles to aid efforts at University College London Department of Computer Science. We focus on how, when and where resources – energy, (raw) materials including water, space and time – are consumed by the building (place), its occupants (people), and their activities (pedagogy). We describe the challenges and difficulties hindering our attempt to quantify the Department’s resource footprint. Beyond this, we find a need to rematerialise the ICT/EEE ecosystem: to reveal the full costs of the seemingly intangible information society by, for example, undertaking analyses of end-user paraphernalia such as smartphones and servers across their entire life history and demonstrating the corporeal nature of terms such as Artificial Intelligence, the Cloud, social media, Big Data, and Smart Cities. We sketch routes to realising three interlinked aims: cap the power consumed and greenhouse gas emitted per person per year, become a zero waste institution, and rejuvenate and (re)integrate the natural and built environments. We propose two maxims to aid policy making and guideline preparation: resource use needs to be both minimised and minimal (reduced in relative as well as absolute terms), and responsible research and innovation encompasses not only decreasing the resource footprint of a research facility, organisation or project, but also considering non-technological solutions to complex real-world problems.

Introduction

The Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) encompasses a range of new technologies that are fusing the digital, physical, and biological worlds and is said to define a new economic, industrial and social paradigm [1], one that “will change not only what we do but also who we are. It will affect our identity and all the issues

associated with it: our sense of privacy, our notions of ownership, our consumption patterns, the time we devote to work and leisure and how we develop our careers, cultivate our skills, meet people and nurture relationships” [2]. At its heart is the digital economy, a complicated mixture of digitisation, data, advanced analytics, software, hardware, operations, and networks [3]. Since digital technologies can reshape the individuals and communities manufacturing and using them [4–7], the social, political, economic, ethical, equity, and similar impacts of the ICT/EEE ecosystem, componentwise and as a whole, are subjects of increasing concern [8–16]. We need new “ways of seeing” [17] this world and understanding its genesis [18, 19]. Since the system in which technology is embedded and technology itself are equally noteworthy, the material nature of the information society warrants greater attention. ICT/EEE-related products, processes, services, and infrastructure are downstream outcomes of research and development performed at universities, companies, the military, and other organisations. Consequently, such institutions could make significant contributions to militating against the deleterious resource-related impacts of the ICT/EEE ecosystem. Realising this potential will require empirical investigations of the resource footprints of academic computer science departments worldwide. Here, we provide an up-close, in-depth, and detailed examination of University College London (UCL) Department of Computer Science, a case study aimed at initiating a conversation on how to create living laboratories for teaching and learning about resource-constrained computing, computation, and communication.

Notwithstanding system challenges [20], Artificial Intelligence (AI) is viewed as a pillar of industrial, business, and industrial strategy, for example, that of the United Kingdom (UK) [21]. Typically, understanding this keystone of the 4IR’s effects on and interaction with society is cast as tasks such as developing (ethical) principles for algorithmic transparency and accountability [22, 23], addressing risks to the privacy and autonomy of individuals, and articulating the legal standing of groups whose composition is dynamic because new members join and old ones leave on an *ad hoc* basis (for example, categories produced by Big Data analytics, demographic groups, people connected by a social network site, and online communities formed in response to crime, transport, health, citizen science or other social concern). Since *physical* machines, networks, and networked systems implement computational abstractions, mediate interactions, and support dynamic groups, the resource-related aspects of the ICT/EEE ecosystem on which AI is produced and deployed require greater examination. That is, the use of AI to solve societal challenges such as economic efficiency, industrial production, and healthcare raises questions of who will be liable when algorithms make mistakes, will the systems be private, secure and transparent, and so on. However, AI itself is a societal challenge, not least because practical matters such as scalability and sustainability (for example, [24]) bring to the fore new types of ethical, social, legal, philosophical and other concerns – for example, the material resources, human labour, and data required to run a large-scale AI system [12]. For instance, “while it is difficult to accurately estimate the energy cost of the AlphaGo system developed by Google DeepMind when it beat the human champion recently in the ancient game of Go, one can safely assume that the machine consumed about four-orders-of-magnitude higher power ... as compared to the nominally quoted power of 20 W for the human brain” [25].

Although 4IR- and digital economy-related discussions are replete with terms such as AI, Big Data, machine learning, cloud computing, social media, platform economy, algorithmic decision-making, digital ledger technology, smart farming, smart cities and the grid, the virtual realm is neither ephemeral nor intangible [26]. Dematerialisation is the reduction in the quantity of materials required to deliver the same level of functionality. However, “the information society promises to dematerialise society and make it more sustainable, but modern office and knowledge work has itself become a large and rapidly growing consumer of energy and other resources” [27]. A simple, quantitative, predictive model for dematerialisation and an empirical examination of 57 case studies found “there is no dematerialization occurring even for cases of information technology with rapid technical progress. Thus, a fully passive policy stance that relies on unfettered technological change is not supported by our results” [28]. Given the fundamental role of universities, companies, the military, and other organisations in determining the current and future directions of the ICT/EEE ecosystem, greater appreciation of the materiality of the knowledge economy could have significant consequences for the short-, medium-, and long-term evolution of digital technology.

This paper takes measure of the energy, (raw) materials including water, space and time footprint of an

academic computer science department in London. First, we provide the broader context for this place-, people- and pedagogy-based interrogation of the Department. This is followed by a bird’s eye view of the Department and examples of the complex, indeterminate and ever changing nature of the challenges we face. Then, we describe the present state of affairs with respect to the resources consumed by the buildings, their occupants and their activities, and suggest some ideas for the future. Next, we sketch three interlinked paths in our roadmap to a more resilient and healthier Department. Finally, we discuss limitations of this investigation and highlight the need for Research Councils UK – as well as analagous national and international bodies elsewhere – to develop new policies and guidelines on the resource footprint of research projects, organisations, and facilities supported by public funds. Since computer science departments have similar missions, those at institutions and organisations elsewhere will be able to draw lessons from the UCL experience described in this case study. That is, our roadmap and high-level principles can be generalised, adapted, and tailored to suit the needs and contexts of university and non-university computing centres elsewhere. Overall, this inquiry highlights the need for a more holistic approach to the governance and assessment of technologies at the physical-digital-biological interface. For instance, stakeholders investigating these and other future spaces can deepen and widen the spectrum of factors taken into account by applying the nine lenses of the FLE⁵SH (F = Financial, L = Legal, E⁵ = Economic, Ethical, Equity, Environmental, and Ecosystem, S = Socio-political, H = Historical) framework [29]. It has been observed “If we really want transformation, we have to slog through the hard stuff (history, economics, philosophy, art, ambiguities, contradictions). Bracketing it off to the side to focus just on technology, or just on innovation, actually prevents transformation.” [30].

Background

Energy consumption and the rebound effect or Jeavons paradox

In the academic and public spheres, there is greater awareness of the vast quantities of power utilised by the ICT/EEE ecosystem and that the anticipated efficiency savings of new technologies or other measures are often partly or completely clawed back by behavioural changes [31–37]. The latter phenomenon – the rebound effect or Jeavons paradox [38] – occurs when innovations in production or consumption induce an increase in energy consumption that offsets the technology-derived saving [39]. Building on the concept of energy efficiency rebound, the circular economy rebound is said to occur when “circular economy activities, which have lower per-unit-production impacts, also cause increased levels of production, reducing their benefit” [40]. Below, we summarise some resource-related features of the ICT/EEE ecosystem.

- *Data centres* “Everyone prefers to talk about the efficiency of individual data centers, or the proportion of renewable energy they use. No one talks much about total energy used by data centers because the figures you get for that are annoying, depressing and frustrating. . . . The plain fact is that, no matter how efficiently we run them, data centers are expanding uncontrollably, and consuming increasing amounts of power. In fact, the efficiency improvements are contributing to the rapid growth.” [41] Based on estimates of current trends, data centres (servers, storage, network equipment, and infrastructure) in the United States of America (US) are projected to consume ~73 billion kWh in 2020 [42]. Data centres consume vast quantities of water during generation and transmission of electricity to the site as well as by cooling systems at the site itself [42].
- *Networks* Nearly all signals are transmitted over optical fibres at some point along their route. Communication networks will need to deploy techniques of scarce resource management to overcome technical limitations (wireless spectrum, common public radio interface, network management, and switching and software) and socioeconomic influences (network neutrality, innovation with the creative industries, latency, and energy) [43]. To control congestion within a data centre network, new approaches are being developed to coordinate transfers of data among large populations of servers [44]. However, if demand for data services such as video continues to grow, the total energy use by communications networks is projected to rival all other energy use [45]. The CAP theorem states that a distributed

system consisting of a set of computing nodes that communicate over some network – each node consists of memory that stores data – can provide only two of the following three properties: consistency (return the right response to a request), availability (return a response to each request) and partition tolerance (support message delays and losses) [46].

- *Distributed ledger technology (DLT) and Blockchain* DLT is a database that is spread across several independent computing devices, updates are constructed and recorded by each participant “node” of the network, and the ledger is not maintained by any central authority or server – voting and agreement on one copy of the ledger by the nodes is conducted by a consensus algorithm; data quality can be maintained by database replication and computational trust [47, 48]. Pioneered by cryptocurrencies such as Bitcoin, blockchains are a form of DLT where data are organised into blocks, the blocks are linked together and secured using cryptography, and entries are updated using an append-only structure meaning previously entered data are not allowed to be altered or deleted [49–51]. The dependability of blockchain-based systems such as Ethereum and Bitcoin [52] are critical for applications such as managing, processing, and tracing financial, legal, physical or electronic assets across a network of parties irrespective of geography [53, 54]. Technical hurdles hindering blockchain from mass adoption include scalability (for example, latency, and network speed, size, reliability, and efficiency), security (for example, network and user privacy), usability (network and user), accountability (for example, trust and data quality), performance, and resource requirements (for example, energy consumption, physical hardware needed to implement computational abstractions, and resilience and robustness of communication network) [55–59] – in essence, information storage efficiency, communication efficiency, and energy efficiency. Non-technical concerns with respect to food sovereignty have been raised [60].
- *Cryptocurrencies* Key sectors of the global cryptocurrency industry (exchanges, wallets, payments, and mining) have large energy footprints [61, 62] with miners recognising the negative environmental externalities of their activities [63]. One question about the feasibility of broad adoption of DLT platforms [64–67] is whether decentralised blockchains can match the performance of mainstream payment processors: scalable and sustainable real-time advanced analytics [68]. Although estimates vary, a recent calculation suggests the electricity consumption of the Bitcoin network is ~ 1.075 GW, roughly one third of the entire country of Ireland [69]. An analysis of stolen bitcoins from legal, economic and engineering perspectives made eight recommendations for future regulation, one proposal being a carbon tax levied on cryptocurrency mined using proof-of-work methods [70]. There is a performance gap: a Visa credit card takes seconds to confirm a transaction whereas the latency of today’s Bitcoin is at least 10 minutes. The former processes 2,000 transactions/sec on average (with a peak rate of 56,000 transactions/sec) whereas the latter achieves a maximum throughput of 7 transactions/sec [71]. In the Bitcoin network of 5,400 full nodes, the cost per confirmed transaction may be as high as \$6.20 – the operational costs (mainly electricity) and capital equipment costs (mining: proof-of-work and hardware, transaction validation, bandwidth, and storage: running cost) [71]. Thus, “fundamental protocol redesign is needed for blockchains to scale significantly while retaining their decentralization” [71].
- *Machine learning* AI is shifting towards the edge, analysing data locally on a sensor or device rather than processing data remotely on a cloud. This trend is fueled by factors such as the high cost of communication, limits on network capacity and architecture, constraints on latency, privacy, cybersecurity, global availability, and the volume and velocity at which data are being generated [72]. Since reducing data movement conserves energy, the joint design of algorithms and hardware can produce energy-efficient dataflows whilst maintaining accuracy, throughput, and cost [73, 74].
- *Computer Numerical Controlled machine tools (3D printers)* The 3D printing process requires both primary and second energy: intrinsic or direct energy needed to change the form and properties of a material and extrinsic or indirect energy consumed by components that realise and support the printing process such as drive motors and environmental health and safety equipment [75]. A life cycle assessment study of a product offering the same equivalent function (eyeglass frames) manufactured

under a digitally supported distributed manufacturing system and a conventional mass scale centralised manufacturing system identified additive manufacturing triggering increased consumption as one threat to the former system’s environmental sustainability [76].

Life cycle analysis: cradle-to-grave

Components of the ICT/EEE ecosystem utilise resources across their entire life history and their environmental and ecological footprint is visible in multiple places: from mining (exploration, extraction, and processing) of non-renewable materials and manufacturing, through production and transportation, to utilisation and disposal [77–80]. For example, the lifespan of modern microwave ovens is nearly seven years shorter than it was almost two decades ago plus their environmental impacts include high levels of electricity consumption, depletion of abiotic elements, human and aquatic toxicities, and creation of photochemical oxidants [81]. However, this cradle-to-grave study considered only the EEE itself. For “smart” microwaves [82], the system boundaries will need to be expanded to include ICT-related resource costs and impacts so their environmental burden can only increase. The percent of tungsten, tin, tantalum and gold consumed by ICT products in 2018 is projected to reach 4%, 0.3% 27% and 5% of global shipments respectively [83]. A study of the recycling of desktop and laptop computers in Belgium found that it saves 80% – 87% of the natural resources compared to landfill and that base metals but not precious metals and plastics were recycled efficiently [84]. Concerns about day-to-day operational use of digital technology include the increasing demand for power, the growing need for raw materials, the generation of ever larger amounts of plastic waste [85, 86] (including by 3D printers [87]), and the emission of greenhouse gases [88]. In 2011, the number of digital electronic and radio-frequency identification-chipped devices connected wirelessly to the internet was projected to reach 50 billion by 2020, or ~ 7 per person [89].

According to the Solving the E-waste Problem (StEP) international initiative, “e-waste” covers all types of EEE and their parts that have been discarded by the owner as waste without the intention of re-use [90]. That is, any household or business item with circuitry or electrical components with power or a battery supply such as computers, mobile telephones, televisions, monitors, laptops, tablets, smartphones, printers, MP3 players, games and gaming equipment, white goods (refrigerators, washing machines, dryers, air conditioners and so on), robots, drones, cables, and routers [91]. E-waste is a product of the largest and fastest growing manufacturing industries: ~ 41.8 million metric tonnes (Mt) was generated in 2014 and could reach 50 Mt by 2018 [92]; the total may escalate to 100 Mt by 2020, probably more given current research and development in areas such as the Internet of Things and wearable technology [93–95]. A study of 50 countries in the pan-European region found that an increase in the gross domestic product at purchasing power parity generates additional e-waste that requires management [96]. Whereas absolute growth of the world economy has a significant influence on the annual growth of atmospheric CO₂ levels, there is no observable relationship between CO₂ concentrations and short-term growth of world population [97].

The ICT/EEE ecosystem affects not just human and environmental health [98–100] but also (agricultural) biodiversity. For example, the electromagnetic radiation of mobile telecommunication antennas can affect wild pollinator abundance and composition [101]. Heavy metals and persistent organic pollutants produced as a result of (in)formal e-waste recycling activities can contaminate soil and water at the recovery site as well as nearby farmland threatening humans, crops, and livestock [102–105]. Current energy and raw material consumption, land use and pollution [102] are key drivers of change of biodiversity for food and agriculture [106] and factors contributing to the degradation and contamination of soil, a non-renewable resource whose preservation is essential if current and future generations are to meet their food, feed, fibre, dye, medicine, fuel, and other needs [107, 108]. *In toto*, the integrity, stability and beauty of natural (agro)ecosystems ought not to be undermined, particularly because agroecology offers solutions to the crises of climate, environment, public health, livelihoods, and economies [109–112].

UCL Department of Computer Science: a bird’s eye view

In order to quantify the Department’s resource footprint, we require full cost accounting models for every activity, product, process, service, and infrastructure: systematic approaches that identify, sum, and report the costs involved in the complete life cycle – from direct private costs, through indirect private costs to social, environmental, and other costs [113]. Clearly, enunciating what we need models for, pinpointing appropriate models, collecting relevant data, and applying models in the real world are non-trivial tasks. To comprehend the magnitude of this task, a short overview of the Department and a brief explication of the activities that take place in pursuit of its goals is useful. These activities take place in specific locations and/or utilise various defined ICT/EEE services. The locations in and of themselves consume resources such as electrical energy, water, and space. Every service consumes resources and requires other hardware and software for its operation. The manufacture, transport, installation, and decommissioning of physical hardware generates greenhouse gas emissions and waste. For each activity, the agents or actors involved include not just staff and students but also external providers such as the higher organisational and academic structures in which the Department is embedded. Some factors can be quantified fairly precisely (for example, the electrical power consumed by a server and the number of bits through a network port), others can only be approximated because they pass outside the control of the Department (for example, hardware manufacturers), and many, if not most, cannot be measured at all (but it may be possible to determine their contribution to the total).

The following activity exemplifies our challenge. The Department has decided to provide a new undergraduate module on Machine Learning, a decision expected to enhance the teaching provision and reputation of the Department as well as UCL. This new module is likely to attract an additional 20 students in the 2017 – 2018 academic year, a number that may increase in subsequent years if the course proves popular. The students require physical space in the form of, for example, classrooms that require heating, ventilation, cooling and electrical power. The ICT/EEE services they need will consume resources. To facilitate teaching, two new GPU servers are to be provided: these require 6U of rack space and add an extra 3 kW to the power drawn by the Department. This in turn requires an equivalent amount of cooling. Whilst the resources consumed during their production and transport are not disclosed by the manufacturer, their packaging consists of ~ 25 kg of cardboard, expanded polythene foam, and the pallet on which they are transported. These are disposed of by UCL through an external recycling company. The servers also utilise a portion of the existing network and storage infrastructure. The course uses a cloud software package, provided free of charge by the vendor, but this adds additional network load throughout the path, and consumes resources wherever the vendor is hosting the cloud application. The bandwidth consumed by the application can be measured on the departmental router, allowing an estimate of Watts per bit to be established.

The servers will be used for the course for 3 – 4 years, after which point they will be replaced by the next generation of server. The Department will continue to operate the hardware as part of a general compute/GPU cluster for an additional 3 – 4 years. As this period will exceed the hardware’s “normal” lifespan, each component will be out of warranty and so not replaced as it fails. Any useful parts which are compatible with other devices (such as power supplies) will be kept – but these need to be stored and as is often the case, may never see usage again. On final removal from the Department, UCL Estates & Facilities disposes of the hardware through an external e-waste company. In the absence of information about the company’s practices, it is unknown how much material is ultimately extracted, whether this is recycled into the manufacturing process, and the energy costs of either or both. Machine learning-related teaching and research occurs in academic computer science department worldwide so although the exact settings and precise circumstances will vary from place to place, many of the problems and difficulties we have described will be familiar.

The heterogenous nature of the Department’s research and funding sources is reflected in the bespoke nature of the research infrastructure and data centre. It is no surprise therefore, that whenever we wish to calculate a metric such as data throughput, CPU cycles, power, and temperature when attempting to ascertain consumption of a particular resource, we need to expend a substantial amount of time and effort gathering consistent and relevant information from a plethora of agents and actors. We expect other academic computer science departments wishing to determine energy efficiency metrics for their data centres [114] will face similar hurdles.

Place – the built environment

Present state of affairs

Multi-site organisation

The Department is spread over two mixed-use multi-storey buildings with one containing a data centre that operates round the clock. We have access to the size of individual spaces – shared offices, laboratories, cubicles, conference rooms, lifts, lobby areas, kitchen/break rooms and so on – but only the water or energy used by the entire building is available. For example, the data centre occupies a total floor area of $\sim 130m^2$ but the resource consumed by this specific space cannot be determined. The most recent Commercial Buildings Energy Consumption Survey from the US Energy Information Administration showed that “office buildings with data centers have significantly higher computing, cooling, and total electricity intensity (consumption per square foot) than office buildings without data centers” [115]. Since the Department’s data centre space is likely to use orders of magnitude more electrical energy than standard office space, we expect a similar disparity between our two buildings.

Data centre

The data centre is the most important wired/wireless network domain in the Department. As the major infrastructure component powering the networked computer system, it is key to productivity and sustainability, both financial and environmental. Data Center Energy Productivity (DCEP) quantifies the useful work that a data centre produces based on the amount of energy it consumes where “work” is defined by and specific to an organisation [116]. Global metrics for different aspects of a data centre include Power Usage Effectiveness (the ratio of the total energy of the data centre divided by the ICT energy consumption), Green Energy Coefficient (the portion of a facility’s energy that comes from green sources), Energy Reuse Factor (the portion of energy that is exported for reuse outside the data centre), and Carbon Usage Effectiveness (assessment of the total greenhouse gas emissions). How best to use these metrics, individually or in combination, to compute the Department’s DCEP requires further inquiry. Given a baseline value however, we could assess the efficacy of interventions – for example, whether particular building-dependent design measures (especially for the rooms containing cooling equipment and servers) reduce electricity use and save money without compromising reliability, availability and resiliency. Practical issues preventing us from determining values for the global metrics include the lack of data, the incomplete and uncertain nature of the data we do have, the pace of change, and the paucity of suitable assessment tools.

Cloud computing services

Many organisations are turning to cloud computing as the way to solve some environmental issues. By utilising resources managed and run by multi-national organisations whose *raison d’être* is profit, the prevailing view is that in order to offer competitive pricing to prospective customers, the company needs to reduce its financial costs by ensuring its computing is as energy efficient as possible. However, this assumption of green computing may not always be a simple matter of comparing data centre efficiencies and the true environmental cost of using cloud computing services is an open question [117, 118]. Nonetheless, there are some benefits to be had for correctly scaled elastic computing. Bursts of high demand can be moved to regional resources where demand can be evened out. The primary challenge is software: getting workflows to seamlessly integrate local services with the on-demand elastic resource, that is, improving a network’s ability to scale up and down as traffic demands ebb and flow.

Keeping bits alive

In many respects, the core function of the Department’s infrastructure (software, hardware, and physical floorspace) and operation (services and people) is to ensure the survival of bits. In principle, we could partition the complete cost of maintaining one byte over a period of time such as a month or a year into the costs of

storage (£/Mbyte), computing (£/CPU cycle), and networking (£/bit). Our challenge is finding, applying, and evaluating models for computing these quantities.

Ideas for the future: architectural works designed with nature for resource conservation and quality of life

Integrating the built and natural environments

A holistic approach is needed to understand the diverse and complex building-related factors that influence human health and performance [119]. Although “green buildings” tend to be discussed from the perspective of their use of environmentally friendly materials and energy-saving techniques, such practices have the added benefit of boosting indoor air quality thereby improving people’s well-being. For example, residents who moved from conventional low-income apartments to “green” homes report substantially fewer “sick building syndrome” symptoms such as headaches and itchy or burning eyes, ailments commonly linked to indoor air pollution [120]. Incorporating indoor and outdoor vegetation into building projects, whether new or renovations, reduces energy use, noise, operation costs, and resource consumption whilst improving occupant comfort, well-being, and productivity [121–125].

The architecture, construction materials, and geographic organisation of the Department’s (multi-site) facilities are key determinants of the land, carbon, energy, and water usage of a building. Accounting for direct and indirect use of resources requires an integrated approach, one that recognises multiple interdependent challenges. For example, water is used in all phases of energy production and energy is required to extract, pump, and deliver water for use by humans, to heat and cool buildings and equipment, and to treat wastewater before it is returned to the environment. Creating a more healthy, sustainable, and resilient Department will require investigating the mutually instructional relationships between a building’s physical infrastructure, what is in it, and what is around it as well as how the biotic and abiotic components of this triad drive the quality of life of the building’s occupants. For example, microorganisms can drive indoor air quality because although they found on surfaces and throughout the water and other systems of buildings, air is likely the most important medium for their dissemination.

Passivhaus

A passivhaus is “a building in which thermal comfort can be achieved solely by post-heating or post-cooling the fresh air flow required for a good indoor air quality, without the need for additional recirculation of air.” [126] The fabric first approach of this robust, proven and cost-effective construction concept produces energy efficient, comfortable and affordable buildings [127]. For example, the Bagley Classroom at the University of Minnesota Duluth campus serves as a multi-purpose assembly space and environmental studies centre and is used by engineering students as a living laboratory to monitor the performance of a passivhaus building and to learn about its construction and systems [128].

A passivhaus building for the Department would need to accommodate the unique and often contradictory energy (electrical and heat) and other needs of machines and humans such as cooling [129, 130], the interior volume of a space [131], and heating [132]. Other challenges range from understanding building physics through cost implications during the design, build, operation, and whole life cycle to quality assurance and onsite delivery. A bespoke building designed for the Department’s geographic location that is part also of a solar oriented university campus, neighbourhood, and city could make important contributions to reducing energy usage as well as enhancing human and environmental health [133–135].

Ecological sanitation

Between 1879 and 1883, UCL’s Main Building was host to the Parkes Museum, an institution which featured a display of over 30 toilets and provided education about hygiene and public health issues to both professionals and the general public [136]. Problems with the modern bathroom and sanitation systems [137, 138] highlight the importance of ecological sanitation, the design and operation of hygienically safe, economical, and closed-loop systems to convert human excreta and urine into nutrients and water to be returned to the soil and

land, including for sustainable food production. For example, a system in a student dormitory in Norway treats in the same process wastewater from toilets (blackwater) and from kitchens and showers (greywater) thereby reducing water consumption substantially, nearly eliminating pollution, and producing a valuable plant fertiliser and soil amendment product [139]. A decentralised urban greywater system installed below-ground in the courtyard of a large multi-apartment building in Oslo Norway requires about 1m² of space per person and includes an above-ground flow form system for additional aeration in the summer that adds aesthetic value – part of the treatment area is utilised also as a playground [140, 141]. The need for a secondary sewer collection system is reduced because the high quality effluent is suitable for use in urban settings, discharge to small streams or open waterways, irrigation or groundwater recharge.

Given the first-hand knowledge and practical experience in Norway, California and worldwide [142–149], ecological sanitation system capable of achieving nearly zero emission and almost complete recycling in London are possible. A holistic approach will be needed when designing compact and technically simple blackwater and greywater treatment systems [150, 151] for the Department. Bathrooms [152, 153] able to generate effluent that could be received by local bodies of water would reduce the need for a secondary piping and pumping system to transport untreated wastewater and contribute to a cleaner city and river Thames [154].

Rainwater harvesting

Rainwater harvesting is the process of intercepting rainfall for its eventual beneficial reuse [148, 155]. Rooftops, concrete patios, driveways and other impervious surfaces of buildings and landscapes can be designed to maximise the catchment area. The collected, detained and retained water could be routed for use in evaporative coolers, toilet flushing, irrigation and so on. An alternative water source for the Department could reduce water (and indirectly energy) consumption and costs by helping to conserve potable water supplies and the amount of runoff the municipal stormwater management infrastructure needs to handle. A rainwater harvesting system would be advantageous to the Department and contribute to making London more resilient to flooding [156].

Agroecologically productive landscape

Similar in many ways to agroecology [109, 157–160], permaculture is an approach to sustainable development that integrates land, resources, people, and the environment through mutually beneficial synergies by imitating the no waste, closed loop systems seen in diverse natural systems [161]. Demonstration permaculture projects for students and/or staff exist at the Department of Educational Sciences Middle East Technical University [162], the University of Massachusetts Amherst [163], and the University of Sussex [164]. A UCL-wide agroecology initiative could transform marginalised landscapes such as underused grass lawns into diverse, educational, low-maintenance and edible gardens that have the added virtue of increasing biodiversity across the campus. Water-wise buildings and surrounding landscapes could be achieved by efforts such as reusing greywater, collecting rainwater, installing waterless composting toilets, and implementing horticultural changes.

Microbiomes

Biological and non-biological ecosystems provide place-based habitats and residences to microbial communities. Tremendous numbers and diverse species of microorganisms colonise not just the surfaces and inner tissues of plants and animals but also settle on the inside and outside of buildings such as offices and hospitals, modes of transport such as cars and trains, conduits conveying fluids and electrical cables, and other infrastructure [165–167]. Although the (a)biotic host, climate, geology, and geography affect the local composition, dynamics and impacts of microbiota, microbiomes form a globally interconnected continuum. The number of microbes exceeds the number of cells of the human body and whilst most are harmless and many are beneficial, the consortium is characteristic of the individual: bacteria swabbed from the surfaces of computer keys, computer mice, and mobile telephones match the microbes on their owner’s skin more closely

than those from other people [168, 169]. The bacterial makeup of a building housing a college of business is affected by the number, type and layout of its spaces (offices, classrooms, restrooms, and hallways), the number and variety of their occupants, and the activities occurring within them [170].

Since a Departmental building's overall architecture (notably heating, ventilation and air conditioning systems), intended human use pattern for spaces, and local horticulture affect the the biogeography of its microbial communities, redesign and/or renovation projects should take such factors into account. For example, mechanical ventilation is likely best suited for unoccupied and/or infrequently used spaces: (un)filtered inside or outside air is supplied via dedicated mechanical air handling units to areas such as those needed for building support (machine and server rooms, especially if some microorganisms could physically degrade hardware), storage spaces, mechanical equipment rooms, and janitor closets. In contrast, natural ventilation is necessary to promote a healthy indoor environment and to enhance the life quality of building occupants: unfiltered outdoor air is supplied via window, louvers or other means to areas needed for specific functions such as classrooms, hallways, atria, common rooms, and bathrooms.

People – a building's occupants and visitors

Present state of affairs: education and engagement

Environmental Responsibility Co-ordinator

The Department's Green Champion addresses risks from activities and sets policy and standards for topics ranging from sustainable working (issues such as recycling, disposal and energy use) through co-ordinating, reviewing and ensuring that students are taught relevant environmental and sustainability issues (*cf* a Health and Safety Officer). Open to all members of the Department, the Green Team considers short-, medium- and long-term issues and initiates actions such as encouraging users of the communal coffee machine in the staff common room to empty the grounds into the adjacent bin thereby facilitating composting and/or horticultural use of this organic matter. Another example is making representations to UCL authorities about shared data centre inefficiencies.

Staff and students

The Technical Support Group (TSG) supports the teaching and research needs of faculty. Examples include repairing equipment so it can be reused, designing high performance computing flows to minimise idle times incurred by waiting for external task such as accessing storage to be completed, and moving the majority of services to virtual servers. Since resource use by and in buildings is intimately tied to the behaviour of its occupants, the TSG provides information and instruction for undergraduate and post-graduate students, notably those just entering the Department, as well as visitors such as primary, secondary and tertiary level teachers and pupils. Examples include implementing a printer quota, discouraging unnecessary printed material whilst promoting double-sided printing as default, collecting spent batteries, and using renewable batteries for student robots. Decommissioned equipment is generally offered to students for re-use before final disposal. A hot-desking office space is available to post-graduate students and staff, allowing access to services via a thin client, or direct connection of a laptop; this saves the need for a permanent desk and personal computer.

Ideas for the future: curricula, modules, materials, and activities

Meetups for staff and students

To increase awareness of problems, promote potential solutions, and identify topics which dovetail with existing teaching- and research-related classes and courses, the Department could organise informal gatherings on topics ranging from the materiality of hardware and software through the resource-related aspects of data centres to reasons for the growth in data from social media, mobile devices, sensors, sciences, and other sources. Transport provides one forum for exploring energy efficiency rebound and circular economy

rebound [40]. Strategies for achieving sustainable mobility are (1) efficiency: environmental problems caused by transport can be improved by developing new and more efficient technologies to replace old, inefficient, and polluting materials and methods, (2) substitution: a change to less polluting or more energy-efficient means of transport, and (3) volume reduction: efficiency and substitution are insufficient meaning fundamental changes in behaviour and consumption patterns are required – people must travel less, and freight volumes must decrease [171]. However, these three travel strategies are associated with the rebound effect [171]. Since the circular economy focuses only on a small part of total resource use [172] and may fail to deliver on its potential once economic realities are considered, “what is truly required to reduce environmental impact is less production and less consumption” [40].

Informational resources and material created elsewhere

The Department could produce bespoke versions of extant EEE/ICT-related flyers, documents, and practical information for dissemination to staff, students, and visitors. We provide three examples. First, the Electronic Product Environmental Assessment Tool [173] is an easy-to-use repository utilised by public and private entities in more than 42 countries – federal agencies, state governments, universities, hospitals, hotels, businesses and so on – to make informed purchasing decisions about electronic products based on standards that cover reduction/elimination of environmentally sensitive materials, use of preferable materials, design for reuse, recyclability and longevity, energy conservation, responsible end-of-life management and corporate performance, and reduced and preferable packaging. Second, StEP has a brochure describing its activities such as developing and implementing e-waste strategies on a local, national and international level: reducing the materials used in manufacturing, reusing equipment or components when practical, refurbishing where possible, recovering materials from obsolete equipment, and recycling the highest possible level of material [174]. Third, Engineers without Borders Spain has a brochure posing questions to ask before buying an ICT/EEE item: Do I really need it?, Does the price include the real cost?, What is behind the brand?, What if I don’t find an ethical product but I still need it?, and What do I do with the device when I want to replace it? [175].

ICT/EEE community clinics and cafés

The Department could hold regular hands-on events to diagnose malfunctioning, repair broken, and repurpose neglected items; practical activities in accord with the StEP initiative’s addition of Refurbish and Recover to the traditional “Rs” of Reduce, Reuse and Recycle [174]. A natural partner would be UCL’s Institute of Making, a multidisciplinary research club for making, breaking, and repairing everything from jewellery to robots – a facility located on the ground floor of one of the buildings housing the Department [176].

Show-and-tell sessions centred on “ethical” ICT/EEE

The Department could facilitate discussions about the entire physical, financial, and resource life cycle of specific products or items as a way to probe broader philosophical questions such as socioeconomic impacts, alternatives, and social, environmental, ethical, health and labour issues [177–180]. Activities could range from examining the earliest stages of design [181, 182] to defining Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment impact categories related to social and economic issues [183]. For instance, discussants could compare and contrast the “Fairphone” [184] with other smartphones on the market. For each mobile device, questions include How free is it of minerals sourced from conflict zones (for example, gold, tin, tantalum and tungsten)?, To what degree is it manufactured in factories that meet stringent ethical and environmental standards (for example, fair labour conditions for the workforce along the supply chain)?, and What features reduce the level of e-waste (for example, charging batteries from a micro-USB port and multiple SIM slots that permit the same handset to be used for home and work)? [185]. Is it time to move from “Science Finds–Industry Applies–Man Conforms” to “Science Discovers–Humanity Decides–Technology Conforms” [186, 187]?

Problem-based learning about the impacts of ICT/EEE

Small groups of individuals from and outside the Department could collaborate to investigate the known and less obvious real-world consequences of the ICT/EEE ecosystem for humans and ecosystems ranging from negative impacts being shifted from one place to another to genuine efficiency gains arising from adoption being usurped by increasing overall production and consumption and hence waste generation [37, 188–190]. With respect to the rebound effect, energy efficiency increases in ICT/EEE cause structural changes in households, education, business, and the military efficiency that result in a proliferation of devices and thereby increasing energy consumption [191]. Similarly, digital fabrication using 3D printers (the conversion of a digital design into a physical object) does not necessarily reduce energy use and transport-associated emissions compared to providing the same products through conventional manufacturing [33, 76]. How ICT/EEE affects the lives of ordinary people – a futurology from below [192] – could be investigated using multicriteria mapping, an interactive hybrid qualitative/quantitative appraisal method for exploring the contrasting perspectives of diverse stakeholders on complex issues [193, 194]. Ecological and economic impacts could be studied through an ecological economic analysis in a problem-based learning setting [195, 196].

As illustration, consider the potential human health problems associated with the normal operation of 3D printers and environmental concerns associated with their plastic products. These machines can use a variety of raw materials (for example, thermoplastics, metal and ceramic powder, and cells) to produce objects as diverse as trinkets, eye glasses and organs [197]. Typical commercially available desktop machines heat plastic feedstock, extrude it through a small nozzle, and deposit it onto a surface to build the object, a process that emits extremely high levels of ultrafine particles (UFPs, particulate matter under 100 nanometres in diameter) [198]. Epidemiologic research suggests that exposure to mass concentrations of atmospheric UFPs increases adverse cardiovascular and respiratory problems and might contribute to pre-term birth [199, 200]. Large, single plastic items degrade ultimately into millions of microplastic pieces and these millimetre or smaller sized particles have the potential to cause physical and toxicological harm to zooplankton, fish and a wide range of other organisms [201, 202]. Based on data obtained from 24 expeditions (2007-2013) across all five sub-tropical gyres, coastal Australia, the Bay of Bengal and the Mediterranean Sea, a minimum of 5.25 trillion plastic particles weighing 268,940 tons are estimated to be afloat at sea [203]. Indeed, “given the concerns over microplastics, the temptation may be to ‘clean up the mess,’ but substantial removal of microplastic debris from the environment is not feasible. Identification and elimination of some of the major inputs of plastic waste is a more promising route, as is reduced consumption and the recognition of plastic waste as a resource.” [201]

Zero waste

The Department could investigate zero waste’s guiding questions and business principles [204] in light of its own needs and practices. Zero waste seeks to “guide people in changing their lifestyles and practices to emulate sustainable natural cycles, where all discarded materials are designed to become resources for others to use. Zero Waste means designing and managing products and processes to systematically avoid and eliminate the volume and toxicity of waste and materials, conserve and recover all resources, and not burn or bury them. Implementing Zero Waste will eliminate all discharges to land, water or air that are a threat to planetary, human, animal or plant health.” This framework includes the following lenses.

- “*Rethink* What has led us to our present linear use of materials and thus, what needs to evolve to move towards a closed loop model? How do we re-design systems to avoid needless and/or wasteful consumption? Reduce: What supports the use of less material and less toxic material? Reuse: What supports the better use of those products we already have in ways that retain the value, usefulness and function? Recycle/Compost: How do we ensure materials are put back in the materials cycle? Recover: What was salvaged from mixed waste? Residuals Management: What is still left and why? What do we need to take out of the system that should not have been circulated in the first place? How do we manage what is left in a flexible manner that continues to encourage movement towards Zero Waste? Unacceptable: What systems and policies encourage wasting and should not occur?”

- “*A commitment to the triple bottom line* Apply the Precautionary Principle before introducing new products and processes. Send zero waste to landfill or incineration. Take financial and physical responsibility for products and packaging. Buy reused, recycled and composted products in all aspects of operation. Prevent pollution and reduce waste by redesigning supply, production and distribution systems. Adopt highest and best use hierarchy (reuse product or materials for their original purpose, for an alternate purpose, for their parts; recycle sustainably inorganic materials in closed loop systems and in single-use applications; and compost or mulch organic materials to sustain soils, avoid use of chemical fertilisers, reduce erosion and litter and retain moisture). Economic incentives for customers, workers and suppliers to maximise the reuse, recycling and composting of discarded materials. Products or services sold are not wasteful or toxic. Use non-toxic production, reuse and recycling processes.”

Zero footprint

The Department could devise activities built on the Zero Footprint Campus project, an art programme in the public areas of the Utrecht Science Park that examined the (im)possibilities of sustainability [205]. For instance, “To find out if human power can sustain a modern lifestyle, we are designing plans to convert a 22 floors vacant tower building on the campus of Utrecht University in the Netherlands into an entirely human powered student community for 750 people. We’re also constructing a working prototype of the human power plant that supplies the community with energy. The Human Power Plant is both a technical and a social challenge. A technical challenge, because there’s a lack of scientific and technological research into human power production. A social challenge, because unlike a wind turbine, a solar panel or an oil barrel, a human needs to be motivated in order to produce energy.” [206]

Learning and adapting ideas from other fields

Researchers in Cyber Risk and Resilience Management have developed a framework for identifying, analysing, and resolving vulnerabilities in an organisation’s operating environment [207]. The “CIA” triad is a simple but widely-applicable model for information assets used in the information risk industry: any secure system should guarantee Confidentiality (the ability to hide information from those people unauthorised to view it), Integrity (the ability to ensure that data are an accurate and unchanged representation of the original secure information) and Availability (the ability to ensure that the information concerned is readily accessible to the authorised viewer at all times). In order not to incur fines from the Information Commissioners Office, for each new risk, an organisation measures and assigns risk coefficients for CIA which are then evaluated in terms of accept, avoid, transfer or reduce. Similarly, the Department could assign a number to a new ICT/EEE purchase or service based on principles and considerations such as the StEP initiative’s Reduce, Reuse, Recycle, Refurbish, and Recover [174]. This figure would be employed to determine whether the item is to be accepted, avoided (use an existing service), transferred (use elastic computing) or reduced (does it need to be operated at all times).

Pedagogy – teaching, learning, investigating and other activities

Present state of affairs: classroom

Green computing

Green IT is the “study and practice of designing, manufacturing, using and disposing of computers, servers and associated subsystems – such as monitors, printers, storage devices and networking and communications systems – efficiently and effectively with minimal or no impact on the environment. Green IT also strives to achieve economic viability and improved system performance and use, while abiding by our social and ethical responsibilities” [208]. Environmental sustainability, the economics of energy efficiency, and the total cost of ownership (including that of disposal and recycling) fall under the rubric of “green” computing. Ideas such as green networking and energy-aware security [209] are of practical and theoretical relevance:

from materials to devices to circuits to complete systems, fundamental limits to computation exist in areas such as manufacturing, energy, physical space, design and verification, and algorithms [210]. Currently, the Department has few undergraduate and/or post-graduate courses, reading groups, or other vehicles that could be categorised as addressing green computing-related problems and solutions.

Ideas for the future: resource-constrained computing, computation and communication

Resource-efficient computing, algorithms, and security

By weaving the concept of resource-constrained computing, computation and communication into the fabric of instruction, research and development, the Department could chart a course to ensuring resource use is both minimised and minimal. For example, a recent study sought to quantify the financial and environmental costs of training a variety of popular off-the-shelf neural network models for natural language processing (estimates of kilowatts of energy consumed were converted to approximate carbon emissions and electricity costs) [211]; model inference is also a problem [212]. Elsewhere, developers of software systems are being encouraged to consider not only the technical and economic requirements but also the social and environmental dimensions [213]. Indeed, addressing topics such as reducing power and raw material consumption, lowering the financial costs of computation and digital preservation, decreasing carbon emissions, lessening environmental impact, improving systems performance and use, and saving physical space are deemed necessary for enabling smaller, lighter, faster, cheaper, and cooler ICT/EEE hardware and software [214, 215]. Since using less energy produces less heat waste yielding higher clock speed, reversible computing is one potential solution [216, 217]. With respect to developing, training, testing and running models, “green AI” advocates evaluating accuracy as a function of computational and financial costs [24]. Research topics of interest include quantifying the resources required to achieve a given level of efficiency in hardware (computing), software (algorithms), and security (information transmission in the presence of adversaries and eavesdroppers).

A Living Laboratory for Experimental Computer Science

The TSG could explore the feasibility of creating a fully functional machine room that simultaneously enables and facilitates staff and students to observe, monitor, and investigate the operation and behaviour of a complex real-life computing facility. The resultant information could be used to define, refine, and implement solutions for reducing the Department’s resource footprint. Unfortunately, it is difficult to calculate efficiency because the latest processors will switch processing speed depending on workloads but will cap these turbo speeds if particular instructions are used [218]. The TSG is performing experiments to ascertain which processor model is best suited to particular job types.

A Back to the Future Interest Group

Informal grouping of staff and students from different strands of computer science and other disciplines could re-examine historical technologies and approaches with a view to informing the present and future, culturally and practically. Consider the rebound effect or Jeavons paradox [38, 185]. This counterintuitive notion of expected savings not being (fully) realised because of induced demand dates back to the industrial revolution: the more efficient use of coal made possible by technology caused the extraction and consumption of more coal rather than the preservation of existing reserves [219]. Recent work on systemic drivers of this phenomenon concluded that “sustainability cannot be achieved by technological innovations alone, but requires a continuous process of institutional and behavioral adjustment” [220]. In the late 19th century, the nature and availability of materials such as rubber, gutta percha, copper and hessian shaped development of the telegraph and transatlantic communication [221]. Virtually every technology invented in the last 30 years – smartphones, wind turbines, hybrid cars, MRI scanners and so on – uses rare earths (lanthanides) such as dysprosium, neodymium, terbium, europium, and yttrium and rare gases such as helium [222, 223]. Rising

demand in the green/clean/alternative technology sectors is depleting rapidly the world’s entire supply of strategic materials [224, 225]. What lessons can be drawn from the past’s understanding of technology’s materiality?

Modern subjects such as latency, bandwidth and delay (disruption) tolerant networks could draw on the 18th century optical telegraph, a communications network for forwarding coded messages over long distances without the need for wires, electricity, horses or postmen and an e-mail system that could achieve transmission speeds of ~1,400 kilometres per hour [226]. From early antiquity, private persons, governments, the military, press agencies, stockbrokers and others have used carrier pigeons to convey messages; one unexpected virtue of such systems is pigeon guano [227], a substance prized as a super-manure since the Middle Ages and regarded as more valuable than that of other birds. Indeed, sneakernets – the physical transport of classical information stored in removeable media – are used today [228–231] and have been proposed as a low-latency high-fidelity network architecture for quantum computing across global distances: ships carry error-corrected quantum memories installed in cargo containers [232]. Transmitting information using inscribed matter has its virtues [233, 234].

The challenges of digital preservation are technical (rendering accurately authenticated content over time), financial (using limited resources to maximise the value delivered to future users), and legal (the public, private and criminal law covering the initial conservation and subsequent reuse of and access to data, metadata, documents, and software) [235]. Whereas the environmental and economic costs of digital preservation are known [215], less well appreciated are practical consequences of technical properties such as the “fragility of academic communication in the Web era as opposed to its robustness in the paper era” [236]. That is, the root cause of the evanescent Web [236] can be described as follows: “in the paper world in order to monetize their content the copyright owner had to maximize the number of copies of it. In the Web world, in order to monetize their content the copyright owner has to minimize the number of copies. Thus the fundamental economic motivation for Web content militates against its preservation.” What is the resource footprint of the policies, strategies and actions needed to ensure that digital information of continuing value remains accessible and usable?

With predictions of 44 zetabytes of data stored by 2020 (a 10 fold increase from 2013), there is a need to adopt “a more aggressive policy of data archiving on long-term, low-energy, ‘cold’ storage” [237]. Given DNA’s remarkable longevity and enormous information density in the natural world [238], this molecule – on its own or inserted into the genome of a living organism – is seen as an attractive medium for archival storage of digital information [239–252]. The key steps [253] in preserving user digital data in strands of synthetic DNA are encoding (converting binary data into a digital nucleotide sequence using an error-correcting code), *de novo* synthesis (fabricating synthetic DNA strands matching the digital nucleotide sequence), storage (preserving DNA molecules in an appropriate environment such as low temperature or encapsulation in silica), management (maintaining large repositories of nucleic acid-based datasets over long periods of time), retrieval (fetching entries from the repository and selectively extracting DNA molecules from storage containers, random data access), sequencing (determining the exact order of nucleotides in the synthetic DNA strands and generating a digital nucleotide sequence), and decoding (translating the digital nucleotide sequence into binary data). Outstanding technical challenges include lowering costs (\$10² for storing 1 megabyte in DNA but \$0.0001 per year using tape), increasing throughput (DNA synthesis and sequencing are inherently slow whereas access times of hard drives are milliseconds), and reducing errors in writing, reading, storage, and handling DNA (mismatches between the information conveyed by the physical material and the digital data theoretically associated with it – for example, complete loss of DNA strands and aggregate insertion, deletion, and substitution rates of ~0.01 errors/base) [246, 254, 255]. From encoding to decoding, information security concerns such as the potential to embed malware in synthetic DNA [256] are underappreciated. In February 2018, it was said that ~10 tons of DNA is needed to store all the world’s data, an amount that could fit in a semi-trailer [257].

DNA-based systems for data storage and other purposes [258, 259] exemplify the 4IR but bring with them, for instance, bio-automation and biotechnology’s cyberbiosecurity threats [260, 261]. What would be the resource footprint of a DNA-based data centre: a full cost accounting of the products, processes, services, and infrastructure needed across the entire life cycle? Cradle-to-grave studies addressing 4IR-related questions

would need to consider the key issues of scalability, sustainability, safety (human and environmental health consequences), security (dual use) and privacy. The intersections of the digital, physical and biological spheres will present new challenges and novel threat categories such as those posed by convolution of e-waste and biomedical/biological waste (b-waste). What impacts would a DNA-based data economy have on the lithosphere, biosphere, atmosphere, and hydrosphere?

A more resilient and healthier Department: a roadmap

Successful development and deployment of a roadmap for the Department requires (1) understanding the basic attitudes, values, and patterns of behaviour that are common to staff and students, including patterns of consumption or non-consumption, (2) rethinking discarded materials as resources, (3) reducing waste so that it is diverted from landfills, incinerators and the environment (no burial, burning, or emission into air, water and land), (4) promoting the interconnected nature of human and environmental health, and (5) scrutinising concepts such as progress and modernity [262–266]. More broadly, it is important to avoid solutionism, “an unhealthy preoccupation with sexy, monumental, and narrow-minded solutions – the kind of stuff that wows audiences at TED Conferences – to problems that are extremely complex, fluid, and contentious. . . . solutionism presumes rather than investigates the problems that it is trying to solve, reaching ‘for the answer before the questions have been fully asked.’ How problems are composed matters every bit as much as how problems are.” [267]

Formulating policies and developing guidelines that create a living laboratory for teaching and learning about resource-constrained computing, computation and communication will require a unique multi-, trans- and inter-disciplinary approach. We will need data pertaining to the technical aspects of resource consumption as well as information and ideas relevant to the architectural, human, and philosophical dimensions of the task. Thus, one potential strategy is the establishment of a resource-aware problem solving laboratory spanning the Department, the Slade School of Fine Art, and the Barlett School of Architecture. By virtue of its ability to examine problems from diverse angles, the resultant UCL Department of (Re)search would be well placed to identify novel and propose unexpected solutions to topics such as energy sufficiency (reducing the growth in energy services) and the floors and ceilings of energy use [268]. Its initial remit might be to explore how the three aims outlined below could be achieved.

Do not exceed 2,000 W and 1 ton CO₂ per person per year

In the 1990s, researchers proposed a pragmatic step towards a sustainable Western lifestyle whereby each person in the developed world – primarily the USA, Canada, Western Europe and Australia – would consume no more than 2,000 W and emit no more than 1 ton of CO₂ per year. Starting with the city of Basel, other regions in Switzerland as well as in Germany have accepted the idea and begun to realise this goal. Assessment of the environmental behaviour of ~4,000 Swiss inhabitants plus a life cycle assessment indicates that whereas restraining energy demand to 2,000 W is possible, limiting CO₂ production to under 1 ton per person per year is difficult [269]. Given the nature and activities of the Department, a scenario where a student or staff member uses under 2,000 W and produces less than 1 ton CO₂ will be a challenge.

As discussed earlier, knowledge of energy efficiency does not necessarily translate into energy savings (technologies designed originally to reduce energy use can give rise to new applications that eventually raise energy consumption as well as technological obsolescence), energy consumption does not equal electricity consumption (an ICT/EEE with a given kilowatt-hours of electricity rating requires the production of more than the equivalent amount of energy because the conversion of one form of energy into another is accompanied by loss of energy), and life cycle analyses may be out of date, incomplete or not exist (the complex life history of technologies involve a cornucopia of parts, materials and processing techniques, each with its own resource requirements) [78, 185, 188]. Obstacles to estimating the Department’s energy consumption include the complexity of the infrastructure coupled with the fast-changing nature and rapid evolution of the networks, methods, assumptions, and models employed by researchers. Given the 2012 global communications network (end-use devices, networks, data centres and manufacturing) is postulated to have consumed 8% of

that year’s global energy production and the ever increasing energy consumption per internet user, a “speed limit for the Internet” has been proposed [270]. Furthermore, reductions in the energy intensity of the Internet (energy utilised per unit of information sent) are more than offset by ever higher total energy use arising from shifting consumption patterns (system level factors) [270]. Self-imposed limits on the demand side of digital communication is one mechanism for ensuring that resource use is both minimised and minimal.

Become a zero waste institution

Resource life cycles can be redesigned so that all products are reused and nothing is sent to landfills and incinerators [204]. Higher than the Pollution Prevention Hierarchy, the Zero Waste Hierarchy of Highest and Best Use considers not just the entire carbon life cycle of materials but also the embodied energy used to extract virgin resources, manufacture a product, and transport a product to market. In essence, if a product cannot be “reused, repaired, rebuilt, refurbished, refinished, resold, recycled or composted, then it should be restricted, redesigned, or removed from production”. Since sustainable resource management is the joint responsibility of producers, communities and politicians, a UCL Department of (Re)search could make contributions in all three areas: industrial production and design at the front end, consumption, discard use and disposal at the back end, and a governmental and regulatory landscape in the middle. A UCL Department of (Re)search could be tasked also with articulating what “zero emission” and “zero energy” buildings [271–274] mean in the context of an academic computer science department.

Rejuvenate and (re)integrate the natural and built environments

Increased exposure to and contact with the micro- and macroorganisms of the biome is believed to be important for immune development and thought to reduce several types of diseases and conditions associated with the modern era [275, 276]. Indoor plants provide beneficial bacteria, positively influencing human health [277]. Thus, the Department’s indoor and outdoor natural environment is vital to providing a healthy and resilient workplace. An agroecological approach to the building’s landscape could enhance the well-being of students, staff, and visitors by, for instance, facilitating the flow of beneficial soil- and plant-associated micro- and macroorganisms indoors. Since some microbes can induce deterioration of building materials and artefacts such as compact discs [278–280], the complex relationships between microbes, animals, plants, humans and the enclosed private and public spaces of the Department warrant close investigation. For example, how the microbiomes of the built and natural environment might affect the day-to-day and long-term operation of ICT/EEE as well as *vice versa*. In general, is it possible to enunciate a “soil-to-soil” [281] approach to ICT/EEE? A philosophy analagous to the seed-to-skin-to-soil approach developed for a hoodie grown, designed and crafted using materials from a 150 mile supply chain where at the end of its life, the nutrients in the composted garment (apart from the metal zip) could be returned to pasture or farmland used to produce fibres and dyes and hence raw materials for subsequent hoodies [282].

Concluding remarks

This case study focused on the problem of characterising and quantifying the resource footprint of an academic computer science department. In addition to the factors discussed here, a full accounting will require identifying and enumerating all manner of externalised costs such as off-site data centres, not least their energy, land, raw material and water requirements. Despite such limitations, practical steps towards a 2,000 W, 1 ton CO₂, zero waste Department where the natural and built environments are (re)integrated do exist. Design philosophies rather than specific technologies are key: for example, passivhaus, ecological sanitation, rainwater harvesting, and agroecology are place-based approaches guided by local landscapes, communities, building materials, and climate. Buildings are not merely mechanical entities which can be deconstructed into parts with certain dimensions – windows and doors of a certain height, area, and volume. Rather, they are socio-ecological networks whose organisation and dynamics are governed both by the physical structure and interactions amongst and between the biotic and abiotic components across wide spatial and temporal

scales. The earlier and faster the Department understands the many facets of resource-constrained computing, computation and communication and mitigates its consumption of resources, the less adaptation will be required in the future. This is because major infrastructure can last for 30 to 100 years and even academic curricula have a lifespan of many years. We propose two maxims to aid policy making and guideline preparation. First, resource use needs to be both minimised and minimal (reduced in relative as well as absolute terms). Second, responsible research and innovation (RRI) encompasses not only decreasing the resource footprint of a research facility, organisation or project, but also considering non-technological solutions to complex real-world problems.

Other academic computer science departments can draw lessons from our findings and use them to develop their own roadmaps. For example, the technology company Nvidia produces graphics processing units (GPUs) for the gaming, cryptocurrency, and professional markets but its DGX-1 supercomputer is aimed at machine learning tasks in high performance data centres, for example, accelerating the use of deep learning by combining GPUs with integrated deep learning software. Our current experiments with Nvidia’s DGX-1 machines show that they each consume ~ 3 kW, and if we are to include the amount of energy required to efficiently cool these systems, then we are consuming ~ 3.5 kW. After many hours (and kWh) of training, a student may identify an image such as that of a cat with close to 100% reliability. How users respond to energy-related information about their computations is a topic for further investigation. Beyond this, one of us (D.A.T.) has direct experience of managing a national computing facility funded by the UK’s Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC, a national research funding agency) and where one of the first considerations was the ability to power such a system [283]. Free to all academic users, this Joint Academic Data Science Endeavour high performance computing resource is designed to support the needs of machine learning and related data science applications at six university partners.

According to the EPSRC, “responsible innovation is a process that seeks to promote creativity and opportunities for science and innovation that are socially desirable and undertaken in the public interest” [284]. Its AREA (Anticipate, Reflect, Engage, Act) framework [285] is an approach that continuously seeks to (1) describe and analyse “the impacts, intended or otherwise, (for example economic, social, environmental) that might arise. This does not seek to predict but rather to support an exploration of possible impacts and implications that may otherwise remain uncovered and little discussed;” (2) reflect on “the purposes of, motivations for and potential implications of the research, and the associated uncertainties, areas of ignorance, assumptions, framings, questions, dilemmas and social transformations these may bring;” (3) open up “such visions, impacts and questioning to broader deliberation, dialogue, engagement and debate in an inclusive way;” and (4) use “these processes to influence the direction and trajectory of the research and innovation process itself.” Similarly, “ProGReSS” is a European Commission-funded project whose mission is to promote a European approach to RRI: “research and innovation which is ethically acceptable, sustainable by avoiding significant adverse effects and drives towards the common good, i.e., societal desirability” [286].

Research Councils UK (RCUK) is the strategic partnership of the EPSRC and seven other funding organisations. Each year, around 3 billion of public money is invested into university research organisations and facilities “covering the full spectrum of academic disciplines from the medical and biological sciences to astronomy, physics, chemistry and engineering, social sciences, economics, and the arts and humanities.” [287] Currently, RCUK has policies and guidelines on open access [288], impact through knowledge exchange [289], and governance of good research conduct [290]. This study highlights the need for new policies and guidelines on the resource footprint of research projects, organisations and (computer) facilities. These could be developed using the findings of a report prepared by a national working group convened by RCUK to investigate this subject.

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